

D2.1: Use Case Specifications (First Version)

PROJECT	
Project Number	101120962
Project Acronym	RESCALE
Project Title	Revolutionised Enhanced Supply Chain Automation with Limited Threats Exposure
Start Date	01.10.2023
Programme	HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-02
DELIVERABLE	
Deliverable Type	Report
Workpackage	WP2
Deliverable Lead	CC
Editors	Marton Sipos
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Dissemination Level	Public

Abstract

This deliverable presents the outcomes of Task 2.1 – Pilots Use Cases Specifications of Work Package 2 – Use Cases Specifications, Requirements and Architecture of RESCALE during its first iteration. It includes the initial description and specification of the two pilot use cases. It provides a static and dynamic overview of the pilots’ components and presents the two involved SMEs. The deliverable also describes the fundamental problems that the pilots face and will solve through the RESCALE project.

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101120962

Document Revisions & Quality Assurance

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Revisions

Version	Date	Partner	Overview
1.0	29/02/2024	CC & PST	Final version
0.9	28/02/2024	UNSPMF & INTRA	Reviewer comments
0.8	15/02/2024	PST	Updated Pilot1 based on partner feedback
0.7	09/02/2024	CC	Updated Pilot2 based on partner feedback
0.6	28/01/2024	PST	Added figure and description to Pilot1
0.5	19/01/2024	CC	Content added to sections 1 and 4
0.4	16/01/2024	PST	Draft description of Pilot1
0.3	16/01/2024	CC	Updated description of Pilot2
0.2	08/01/2024	CC	Draft description of Pilot2
0.1	04/01/2024	CC	Table of Contents and instructions

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
2FA	Two-factor Authentication
API	Application Programming Interface
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
CC	Chocolate Cloud ApS
CI/CD	Continuous integration/Continuous Deployment
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DSCG	Device Supply Chain Graph
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet of Things
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications - Unified Architecture
PST	Peer Stritzinger GmbH
REST	Representational State Transfer
RLNC	Random Linear Network Coding
SaaS	Software as a Service
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SSCG	Software Supply Chain Graph
TBOM	Trusted Bill of Material
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TrustOR	Trust Orchestrator Framework
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VM	Virtual Machine

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the two pilot use cases as part of the first iteration of Task 2.1. It includes their descriptions and their initially collected requirements. It focuses on defining the main problem the uses cases seek to solve as part of the project, what is missing from current state of the art solutions and how RESCALE will solve the main problem. The document is divided into five main sections beyond this executive summary.

Section 1 serves as an introduction to the document. It provides information about the document's purpose, including its role in the RESCALE project, the methodology with which its contents were created, its structure and the audience to which it is mainly addressed.

Section 2 is dedicated to RESCALE's first pilot use case: Auto-Placement Security Aware Augmented Data-Flow and Infrastructure. It describes the use case provider, the pilot's architecture, infrastructure and workflows. It defines the core problems that will be addressed in RESCALE, highlighting any issues with existing approaches. It presents an initial threat model as well as a set of success criteria to serve during the evaluation of the pilot use case.

Section 3 is dedicated to RESCALE's second pilot use case: Privacy-by-Design Distributed Cloud and Edge Storage and matches the structure of the previous section.

Section 4 summarizes the contents of the deliverable and provides a brief description of its role in the project's life-cycle.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this Document

This deliverable presents the first outcomes of the Task 2.1 - Pilots Use Cases Specifications, during its first iteration.

The project adopts a two-cycle approach regarding this task. In the first cycle, the pilots are specified according to what has been described in the proposal including any additional updates that may be required. In the second cycle, the specifications will be refined, taking into consideration all the work that has been done during the first cycle implementations.

Task 2.1 involves the description of the full specification of the RESCALE pilot use cases. Within this task, the partners providing the pilots (Peer Stritzinger GmbH – PST and Chocolate Cloud ApS – CC), in collaboration with those developing RESCALE’s technologies, will refine them to the level of detail required so that their key functional aspects are completely specified. The specifications provided in this deliverable are an important part of the project’s first cycle. They will be used in Task 2.2 in order to extract functional and non-functional user requirements, forming the starting point of Deliverable 2.3 - Technology Analysis and Requirements Specification (first version), due in M6.

Additionally, in the second cycle, all partners will work together to design and specify the required trial procedures and usage scenarios of these applications. These will drive later efforts to define testing, validation, demonstration and evaluation procedures as part of Work Package 5. The specifications will also be updated. The results will be reported in an updated version of this document entitled Deliverable 2.2 - Use Case Specification (final version), provided in M19 of the project timeline. It will feature updates based on the results of the first stage of development and evaluation of the project.

1.2 Methodology

The pilot use cases play a crucial role in establishing many of the goals and requirements of RESCALE. As such, it is important that their own requirements and specifications are collected early in the lifecycle of the project. The partners leading the use cases (use case providers from now on), PST and CC, were provided with the below list of instructions, breaking down the task into smaller steps. Context was given as to how the different parts would be used in the later stages of the project. The project’s proposal was used as a starting point.

- **Overview:** Provide a high-level overview of the pilot use-case, ideally with figures. The goal of this subsection is to gently introduce the reader to the pilot use case and set the stage for the subsequent subsections.
- **System architecture:** Describe the system architecture, including all software and hardware components that will be affected by the solutions developed in RESCALE. Describe the software and hardware supply chain of the Pilot system. The items listed in this section will be the ones that undergo static and dynamic testing by the RESCALE platform

tools and will have an associated entry in the SSCG and/or DSCG parts of the TBOM.

- **Workflows:** Provide a high-level description of one or more relevant workflows that will be examined in RESCALE. Show how the software and hardware components interact with each other. This section will be used to establish the producer-consumer graph of components in the TBOM.
- **Infrastructure and deployment:** Describe the infrastructure and deployment of the pilot application. Detail level should be determined by how relevant these aspects are to RESCALE.
- **Problem definition:** Define the core problem to be solved in RESCALE. The identified issues should more or less match those we will likely tackle in the project. Provide this input based on the discussions in the WP telcos. This part should be kept relatively high-level, as the formalized user requirements are specified separately in Deliverable 2.3.
- **Threat model:** Describe the threat model to be considered during the project. Consider issues relevant to the project's envisioned outcomes.
- **Issues with existing solutions:** Describe the current solutions of ensuring security of software and hardware components, including 3rd party tools in the supply chain (both open-source and proprietary). These solutions will be augmented or replaced by new or enhanced solutions provided by the RESCALE platform. Point out the shortcomings of existing security-related techniques as well as missing security solutions and their justification (e.g., why would they be beneficial). Focus on the missing methods that are targeted in RESCALE. The RESCALE platform will provide solutions that fix the current issues and fill in the holes identified here.
- **Impact of RESCALE on the pilot use case:** Provide initial ideas of how the RESCALE platform components will interact with or get integrated into the pilot's systems to carry out the required operations. Refer to the same concepts and components described in the System Architecture subsection. This text will guide the RESCALE platform's system design, specifically its interfaces and integrations with the pilot systems.
- **Success criteria:** Define a list of success criteria that can be used to assess whether the RESCALE platform has met the listed requirements. Be consistent with the KPIs defined in the DoA.

This list, as well as the actual contents of the deliverables, were written after a series of regular discussions on the topic. As a preparatory step, the pilot use case providers were asked to provide a tentative list of high-level goals they wished to achieve in the project. They presented these goals to the technical partners to understand whether they fit within the scope of the project, their complexity and the effort required to implement a solution for them. Following this, the use case providers provided the specifications of their pilot applications based on the previously described instructions.

As part of Task 2.2, the discussions extended to the user requirements of the two pilots. Coinciding with the preparation of this deliverable, an initial list of functional and non-functional requirements was defined to be included in Deliverable 2.3.

1.3 Document Structure

The present deliverable is split into the following major chapters:

- **Introduction:** describes the purpose and structure of this deliverable and its role in the project.
- **Pilot 1: Auto-Placement Security Aware Augmented Data-Flow and Infrastructure:** presents the first pilot use case through the schema described in Section 1.2.
- **Pilot 2: Privacy-by-Design Distributed Cloud and Edge Storage:** presents the second pilot use case through the schema described in Section 1.2.
- **Conclusions and Future Plans:** concludes the document, pointing to how it will be used in the continuation of the project.

Finally, a list of sources that have been referred to in the various sections of the document is included.

1.4 Intended Audience

This document is publicly available and should be of use to anyone interested in the detailed description and specification of the two pilot use cases of the RESCALE project.

2 Pilot 1: Auto-Placement Security Aware Augmented Data-Flow and Infrastructure

2.1 Peer Stritzinger GmbH

Peer Stritzinger GmbH (PST) is a technology company engaged in the development of advanced distributed computing and communication solutions. Founded with a focus on addressing the complexities of data and computation in interconnected digital systems, PST has established itself as a notable contributor in its field. The company's history reflects a commitment to delivering robust, secure, and efficient computing platforms, particularly for Internet of Things (IoT) and industrial applications.

PST possesses specialized expertise in distributed computing, emphasizing the Erlang language ecosystem, which is highly relevant to the RESCALE project. The company has developed a variety of products and intellectual property[1] focused on distributed system design and implementation. This includes implementations of protocols such as OPC-UA[2], DDS[3], and Ethernet TSN, as well as solutions for secure data handling in distributed environments. PST's projects often intersect with critical sectors like Industry 4.0, public transport, and SCADA systems, making its contributions valuable to the objectives of the RESCALE project. Notably, PST has developed a stack that combines unikernels with the Erlang runtime and the GRiSP open-source platform[4], underscoring its capabilities in securing distributed applications and infrastructure.

2.2 Overview

The pilot use-case developed by Peer Stritzinger GmbH (PST) within the RESCALE project aims to address the complex challenges of securing distributed applications in heterogeneous computing environments. This use-case is pivotal in demonstrating the feasibility and effectiveness of the RESCALE project's objectives, particularly in the context of enhancing security and resilience in distributed computing networks

PST is building a new SaaS product called GRiSP.io implementing a holistic Cloud to Edge and IoT/Fog distributed computing platform which focuses on data-flow paradigms and automatic placement of data-flow function blocks to nodes in heterogeneous networks based on compute & network bandwidth, latency and energy requirements. The set of criteria for placement will be expanded in RESCALE by security and trust properties.

At the heart of this use-case is the refinement and enhancement of security mechanisms within the pilot's system architecture, particularly through the lens of the software supply chain and the deployment of distributed applications across heterogeneous computing environments. The RESCALE project's emphasis is on elevating the trustworthiness of software (and hardware) components and binaries through comprehensive evaluation processes. This approach involves a detailed assessment of the software supply chain, underpinned by the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), which serves as a foundational element for establishing trust levels within the system. The TBOM facilitates a deeper understanding of the security posture of software components

and, by extension, the nodes on which these components are deployed.

Furthermore, the RESCALE project contributes to the pilot by automating the evaluation of both software and hardware components, ensuring that third-party segments are scanned for vulnerabilities. This automation extends to the enhancement of the PST platform, facilitated by the integration of the RESCALE vulnerability analysis modules and make it accessible also for the users of the platform. This module is instrumental in promoting a comprehensive security overview of the supply chain, thereby significantly improving the trustworthiness of the deployed software and hardware elements. Additionally, the project enables the extension of existing deployment mechanisms for Erlang systems, facilitating a platform that supports the concurrent operation of multiple Erlang runtimes alongside code in other languages, all within a framework of heightened security isolation. This capability is particularly valuable for managing communications and operations across different trust zones within the network, utilizing the TBOM as a means of articulating and verifying the trust credentials of software and hardware nodes. By focusing on these areas, the RESCALE project directly addresses the need for a secure, reliable, and trusted computing infrastructure, ensuring that all components, from the software supply chain to the network nodes, adhere to the highest standards of security.

Figure 1: Automated Data Flow Mapping

The pilot use-case also explores advanced concepts like automated data flow graph mapping and generalized graph retraction, integrating these with security considerations to optimize network performance without compromising on security. The implications of this use-case are far-reaching, potentially setting new standards for secure distributed computing in various industrial and IoT applications (Figure1).

2.3 System Architecture

The system architecture for the pilot use-case developed by Peer Stritzinger GmbH (PST) within the RESCALE project encompasses a comprehensive suite of both software and hardware components, intricately designed to ensure robust security and efficient performance in distributed computing environments. This architecture forms the foundation upon which the RESCALE solutions will be applied and tested.

Software Components:

- *Erlang Runtime Environment:* At the core of PST’s software architecture is the Erlang runtime, optimized for distributed computing. This environment supports fault tolerance, scalability, and real-time operations.
- *Protocol Implementations:* The architecture includes implementations of various communication protocols such as OPC-UA, DDS, and Ethernet TSN, integral for data exchange and interoperability in industrial settings.
- *Security and Resilience Layers:* These layers encompass functionalities for secure data handling, encryption, and secure boot processes, crucial for maintaining the integrity of the system.
- *Application-Specific Software:* Tailored software solutions for specific industrial applications, including SCADA systems, automated control systems, and IoT integrations.
- *RESCALE Project Tools:* Tools developed under the RESCALE project for static and dynamic testing, vulnerability analysis, and security enhancements will be integrated into the software stack.

Hardware Components:

- *GRiSP Platform:* A key hardware element in the architecture, GRiSP provides an open-source platform for embedded applications, supporting the Erlang runtime.
- *Networking Equipment:* This includes routers, switches, and other networking hardware that support Ethernet TSN and other industrial communication standards.
- *Embedded Systems and IoT Devices:* Various embedded systems and IoT devices form part of the distributed network, each with its own security and computational requirements.
- *Servers and Computing Nodes:* On-premises servers and multicore computing nodes capable of running unikernels and supporting the distributed architecture.

Software and Hardware Supply Chain: The supply chain for the Pilot system in the RESCALE project is critical, encompassing the sourcing, development, and integration of both software and hardware components. The software supply chain includes the procurement of third-party software components, in-house development of custom software solutions, and the integration of RESCALE project tools. The hardware supply chain involves the selection and acquisition of embedded systems, networking equipment, and server hardware, ensuring compatibility and security compliance.

All components listed in this section will undergo rigorous static and dynamic testing using the RESCALE platform tools. They will be part of the Software Supply Chain Graph (SSCG) and/or Device Supply Chain Graph (DSCG) within the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) framework. This process ensures that every element in the system architecture is thoroughly evaluated for security vulnerabilities, aligning with the overarching goals of the RESCALE project to enhance security and resilience in distributed computing environments.

2.4 Workflows

The pilot use-case by Peer Stritzinger GmbH (PST) in the RESCALE project will involve several key workflows that demonstrate the intricate interaction between various software and hardware components. These workflows are essential for understanding the producer-consumer relationships within the system, thereby facilitating the creation of an accurate and comprehensive TBOM.

These are typical workflows that will run on PST's platform, while PST will use RESCALE tools for checking the security of the platform itself they will also integrate some of these tools into the platform to be used by users of the platform developing distributed systems to scan their software and dependencies.

Workflow 1: Data Acquisition and Processing

1. *Data Acquisition:* IoT devices and embedded systems collect data from various sources. This data is then transmitted to the network infrastructure, facilitated by various protocols.
2. *Data Processing:* The data reaches the server nodes where it is processed by application-specific software running on the Erlang runtime environment and containerized function blocks in other languages. This involves computations, aggregations, and preliminary analyses.
3. *Security Application:* Security layers apply encryption and other security measures to the processed data. This step leverages tools from the RESCALE project for static security assessment to identify sensitive data.
4. *Data Storage/Transmission:* The secure data is either stored in on-premises servers or transmitted to other nodes in the network for further use, ensuring integrity and confidentiality throughout the process.

Workflow 2: Software Deployment and Updates

1. *Software Development:* Software components, including protocol implementations and security features, are developed and maintained, often incorporating third-party software elements.
2. *Security Scanning:* Before deployment, the software undergoes static and dynamic testing using RESCALE tools to identify and mitigate vulnerabilities.
3. *Deployment:* The validated software is deployed across the network, affecting various components including servers, embedded systems, and IoT devices.

Workflow 3: Security Aware Automapping

1. *User specified:* Platform user as a creator of distributed IoT applications running on PST's platform labels sensitivity of values and trust in nodes besides e.g. latency, bandwidths, special compute needs. The platform automatically maps function blocks on nodes so that all requirements are met.

2. *TBOM based*: Information from the TBOM about code of function blocks are validated against user labelled sensitivity.
3. *Automatic sensitivity labeling*: User labelling is augmented by automatic sensitivity detection and inference.

These workflows collectively form a comprehensive framework for enhancing the security and efficiency of PST's distributed computing environment through the RESCALE platform, addressing key aspects of data handling, software deployment, and the intelligent mapping of applications within a trusted network infrastructure.

2.5 Infrastructure and Deployment

The infrastructure and deployment strategies for Peer Stritzinger GmbH's (PST) pilot use-case in the RESCALE project are pivotal, encompassing a range of technologies and methodologies that are central to achieving the project's objectives. This section details these aspects, highlighting their relevance to the RESCALE goals.

Infrastructure Components:

- *Computing Nodes*: The infrastructure includes a variety of computing nodes, ranging from high-performance servers to edge computing devices. These nodes are responsible for executing complex computations and storing data.
- *Networking Infrastructure*: A robust networking setup, including routers and switches supporting advanced protocols like Ethernet TSN, ensures efficient data transfer and connectivity among different system components.
- *Embedded Systems and IoT Devices*: A network of embedded systems and IoT devices forms the front line of data acquisition, crucial for real-time monitoring and control tasks in various industrial applications.
- *Security Hardware*: Dedicated hardware for security, such as secure boot modules, secure elements for secret storage and encryption accelerators, enhances the overall security posture of the infrastructure.

Deployment Strategies:

- *Scalable Deployment*: The deployment strategy is designed to be scalable, accommodating varying loads and expanding seamlessly with additional nodes as required.
- *Security-Centric Approach*: A key focus of the deployment strategy is on security. This involves integrating RESCALE's security tools and methodologies at every stage, from initial deployment to ongoing operations.
- *Automated Deployment Processes*: Utilizing automation for software deployment ensures consistency, reduces human error, and enhances the efficiency of deploying updates and patches.

- *Continuous Integration and Delivery (CI/CD)*: A CI/CD pipeline facilitates rapid and reliable software development, testing, and deployment, crucial for maintaining the agility of the system.

Deployment in RESCALE Context: In the context of RESCALE, the infrastructure and deployment strategies are structured to facilitate the integration of RESCALE's tools and methodologies. This includes:

- *Integration with RESCALE Tools*: The infrastructure is designed to seamlessly integrate with tools developed under RESCALE for static and dynamic analysis, and vulnerability assessment.
- *Testing and Validation*: The deployment strategy involves testing and validation of both software and hardware components, utilizing RESCALE's analysis tools to ensure compliance with security standards and project objectives of the whole supply chain.
- *Adaptability and Evolution*: The infrastructure is built to be adaptable, allowing for the integration of future RESCALE developments and accommodating evolving security requirements and technological advancements.

2.6 Problem Statement

The increasing complexity and heterogeneity of computing environments necessitate a sophisticated approach to security, reliability, and efficiency, which existing solutions struggle to fully encompass. The primary issues that the pilot seeks to tackle include:

- **Security and Trust:** Traditional security measures often fall short in providing comprehensive protection across the diverse components of distributed systems. There is a critical need for a unified security framework that ensures the integrity and confidentiality of data as it moves through various trust zones within the network. The reliance on third-party software components and binaries further complicates the trust model, necessitating a robust mechanism to assess and validate their security.
- **Software Supply Chain Vulnerabilities:** The complexity of the software supply chain, incorporating both open-source and proprietary elements, introduces multiple points of vulnerability. Existing tools and processes do not adequately address the identification, assessment, and mitigation of risks throughout the software lifecycle, from development to deployment.
- **Integration and Automation Challenges:** Efficiently integrating and automating the deployment of software across a heterogeneous network of devices remains a significant challenge. This includes the need for secure, automated mechanisms for continuous integration and delivery (CI/CD) that can accommodate the specific requirements of diverse computing nodes. Integrating the RESCALE security assessments into the continuous integration will increase the overall security of the system.

2.7 Threat model

The threat model for the pilot use-case of Peer Stritzinger GmbH (PST) within the RESCALE project encompasses various potential security risks and vulnerabilities that may impact the distributed computing environment. This model serves as a foundation for developing robust security strategies and countermeasures.

External Attacks: The system faces threats from external attackers who may attempt to gain unauthorized access, disrupt services, or compromise data integrity. This includes risks such as network intrusions, denial of service attacks, and malware.

- Attacks through SaaS website, privilege elevation, session hijacking etc.
- Information leakage between VMs on the same machine via transient execution attacks like Meltdown or Spectre. Especially every component that holds key material.
- Side channel attacks via power or timing analysis or similar. Timing analysis is possible remotely and locally whereas the other attacks in this family require physical access. With IoT devices it's not uncommon that they operate in hostile environments, which can provide this kind of physical access.

Internal Threats: Internal threats include risks from within the organization or network, such as unauthorized access or misuse of data by insiders. These threats may be intentional or due to negligence.

- Users of the IoT platform can apply all external attacks
- Developers of software components on the IoT platform that are provided to other users can steal, corrupt and delete data of these users

Data Interception and Manipulation: Given the distributed nature of the network, data transmitted over various channels is susceptible to interception and manipulation. Securing data in transit and at rest is a critical aspect of the threat model.

Hardware and Software Vulnerabilities: Vulnerabilities in hardware components and software applications pose significant risks. These vulnerabilities can be exploited to gain unauthorized access or disrupt system operations. Software vulnerabilities in the supply chain have more and more impact to overall system security. The threat from the supply chain also extends from accidental vulnerabilities to intentional ones which can be harder to detect.

Compliance and Regulatory Risks: Non-compliance with industry standards and regulations, especially in terms of data protection and privacy, is another area of concern. Ensuring adherence to these standards is vital for the integrity of the system.

PST's approach within RESCALE is to address these threats through a combination of advanced security technologies, rigorous testing and validation processes, and continuous monitoring and updating of the system. This proactive stance ensures that the infrastructure remains resilient against evolving security challenges.

2.8 Issues with Existing Approaches

Peer Stritzinger GmbH (PST) currently employs a variety of security solutions to safeguard its software and hardware components, including the integration of third-party tools in the supply chain. While these existing approaches provide a certain level of security, there are notable shortcomings that the RESCALE platform aims to address and improve upon.

Current Security Solutions:

- *Standard Security Protocols:* PST utilizes industry-standard security protocols for data encryption and secure communication. While effective to an extent, these protocols often do not account for more sophisticated or novel attack vectors.
- *Third-Party Security Tools:* The integration of both open-source and proprietary security tools is part of PST's approach. These tools offer functionalities like vulnerability scanning, intrusion detection, and code analysis. However, their effectiveness can be limited by the lack of comprehensive coverage and integration.
- *Manual Security Practices:* Current practices often involve manual processes for security checks and updates, which can be time-consuming and error-prone, leading to potential vulnerabilities.

Shortcomings and Missing Solutions: The existing security measures, while foundational, present several limitations:

- *Lack of End-to-End Security Integration:* There is a need for a more integrated security approach that covers the entire spectrum of the distributed system, from hardware components to application-level software.
- *Inadequate Response on Deployed Systems:* The ability to respond at runtime to security threats is often limited, making the system vulnerable to rapidly evolving attacks.
- *Insufficient Adaptability to New Threats:* Existing tools may not be well-equipped to adapt to new or emerging security threats, especially in the context of advanced persistent threats (APTs) and zero-day exploits.
- *Dependency on Third-Party Tools:* Relying heavily on third-party tools, especially proprietary ones, can create dependencies and potential security gaps due to lack of control and customization.

Justification for Enhanced Solutions: Enhancing or replacing current solutions with those provided by the RESCALE platform is justified by:

- *Need for Comprehensive Security Framework:* A holistic security framework, capable of addressing the unique challenges of distributed systems, is essential for ensuring end-to-end security. This includes a particular emphasis on the supply chain, ensuring that every component, from software development to deployment, is secure and trusted.

- *Requirement for Automated and Integrated Tools:* Automated security tools that are well-integrated into the system architecture can significantly reduce response times and human errors, enhancing the overall security level. This integration is crucial not just within the system's operational boundaries but extends to encompass the entire supply chain, from third-party software components to hardware procurement.
- *Supply Chain Security and Compliance:* Ensuring the security of the supply chain is a critical component of modern cybersecurity strategies. The RESCALE platform aims to provide comprehensive tools for monitoring, analyzing, and securing the supply chain, thereby preventing the introduction of vulnerabilities through third-party components.

2.9 Impact of RESCALE on the Pilot Use Case

The integration of the RESCALE platform within the pilot use-case of Peer Stritzinger GmbH (PST) is anticipated to have a significant and transformative impact. The RESCALE components are designed to interact synergistically with the existing system architecture of PST, enhancing its capabilities and addressing the current limitations. This section provides an initial outline of how RESCALE's components will integrate into and interact with PST's pilot systems.

Integration with Computing Nodes:

- *Enhanced Security Protocols:* RESCALE's advanced security testing protocols will be integrated into PST's computing nodes, including servers and edge devices, to provide stronger and more adaptable security vulnerability detection.
- *Dynamic Vulnerability Assessment:* Continuous vulnerability assessment tools from RESCALE will be implemented to monitor and analyze deployed software, ensuring timely detection and response to potential threats.

Software and Hardware Supply Chain Integration:

- *Supply Chain Security Platform:* The integration of RESCALE's supply chain security tools into the CI that builds the IoT platform will ensure that all software and hardware components in PST's supply chain are secure.
- *Supply Chain Security Users:* Integrating RESCALE's supply chain security tools into the IoT platform itself enables PST's customers to easily maintain the supply chain security of all their components as well as third party components offered on the platform app store.

Enhancements in Embedded Systems and IoT Devices:

- *IoT Security:* IoT and embedded systems in PST's network will be equipped with RESCALE's IoT-specific security solutions, providing robust protection against device-level threats.

- *Firmware Updates and Management:* Firmware management tools from RESCALE will ensure that these devices are always running software scanned by RESCALE's analysis tools.

Automated Deployment and Monitoring:

- *CI/CD Integration:* The integration of RESCALE's tools into PST's CI/CD pipeline will enhance the security and efficiency of the software development, testing, and deployment processes.
- *CI/CD Integration for Platform Users:* The integration of RESCALE's tools into PST's platform integrated CI/CD will enhance the security and efficiency of the software development, testing, and deployment processes for the users of the platform.

The impact of the RESCALE platform on PST's pilot use-case is expected to be extensive, touching every aspect of the system architecture. The platform's components are designed to seamlessly integrate with PST's existing infrastructure, providing enhanced security, efficiency, and adaptability. This integration will not only address the current shortcomings but also prepare the system for future technological advancements and security challenges.

2.10 Success criteria

The success criteria for the integration of the RESCALE platform into PST's pilot use-case are anchored in the achievement of key operational and security enhancements, as outlined in the project's requirements. Firstly, a significant reduction in the incidence and severity of security breaches or vulnerabilities within the system is a primary criterion. This includes the effective detection of threats by static and dynamic testing, demonstrating the robustness of RESCALE's security protocols and tools. Secondly, the seamless integration of RESCALE components with PST's existing system architecture without causing disruptions or performance degradation is crucial. This entails the smooth functioning of automated deployment processes, real-time monitoring systems, and the IoT security framework. Additionally, compliance with industry-standard security practices and regulations, as facilitated by RESCALE's automated compliance tools, is a critical measure of success. Finally, the adaptability of the system to incorporate future security updates and technological advancements, maintaining its resilience against evolving cyber threats, will be a definitive indicator of the long-term success and sustainability of the RESCALE integration.

3 Pilot 2: Privacy-by-Design Distributed Cloud and Edge Storage

3.1 Chocolate Cloud ApS

Chocolate Cloud ApS[5] (CC) is a high-tech start-up based in Denmark with deep MIT roots and with a global perspective. CC delivers software products for efficient and privacy-preserving Multi-Cloud data storage (hybrid clouds[6], multiple public clouds [7], multiple private clouds) as well as a blazing fast technology to reduce storage by a factor of 2 in OpenStack (Object-based storage) and Hadoop (BigData).

CC's vision goes beyond the current Cloud storage market to create solutions that include edge resources and IoT storage devices. This is key in meeting the needs of new emerging low-latency applications, such as those developed to run over 5G networks. To this end, CC has participated in several research projects [8, 9, 10] aimed at developing their unique privacy, security and performance capabilities at the edge of the network. In RESCALE, CC's goal is twofold. First, CC aims to validate and improve the security of their existing products. Second, CC seeks to bring the technology they have developed in previous projects closer to a market-ready state through the tools developed in the project.

3.2 Overview

The second pilot use case centers around Chocolate Cloud's distributed cloud and edge storage solutions shown on Figure 2. Data security and privacy are the key commitments CC makes to its users. All CC products share the same core ideas such as having different layers of encryption to protect data both in transit and at rest and using Random Linear Network Coding [11], an erasure code with privacy benefits. However, CC has yet to implement a comprehensive, holistic security assessment mechanism that covers its entire supply chain. This is an urgently needed development that will be achieved using the tools and techniques developed in RESCALE. Rather than creating novel, custom security mechanisms, the pilot use case will showcase the innovations of the project, relying on them to increase the security of CC's products.

SkyFlok

SkyFlok[12] is Chocolate Cloud's most important product aimed at end-users. It is a secure file storage solution designed to tailor to the needs of both businesses and individuals. It enables users to easily and reliably store their data in the cloud. Compared to competing solutions, it gives customers full control over where their data is stored by leveraging a multi-cloud approach. SkyFlok supports the three major cloud providers (Amazon, Google, Microsoft) as well as several smaller local solutions (OVH, Deutsche Telekom, Orange Business Cloud, IONOS, Exoscale, etc.). Through the use of EU-based providers, SkyFlok offers GDPR-compliant storage through 54 GDPR-compliant locations. This service has been commercially available since Q1 2018 and has had more than 750, mostly SME teams using it since Q1 2020.

Figure 2: Overview of different services and solutions developed by Chocolate Cloud as part of the SkyFlok product family.

SkyFlok for Enterprise

Medium and large businesses (250+ employees) that are SkyFlok customers would like to extend their use of Chocolate Cloud’s SkyFlok service. At the moment, SkyFlok works great for file-based collaboration and file sharing workflows as well as for data archival purposes. However, given its fully cloud-based architecture, it lags behind in terms of latency compared to an on-premises storage solution. By introducing an On-premises Storage Gateway and moving data closer to the edge, download and upload latencies can be greatly improved. While many customers choose SkyFlok over competing solutions thanks to the privacy guarantees it offers, privacy concerns remain a major impediment to more wide-spread adoption of cloud storage in general. Due to legal requirements or internal policies, enterprises want strong guarantees that their data cannot be accessed by third parties, including the storage provider. Conventional cloud storage can only achieve this to a limited degree. Moving the file encryption/decryption process on premises, under full control of the enterprise is key to providing these guarantees.

Chocolate Cloud has developed SkyFlok for Enterprise, a solution that extends SkyFlok by offering edge storage locations to customers who already own the required hardware or are willing to invest in on-premises storage infrastructure. These devices will show up in SkyFlok and will be used in combination with the traditional cloud-based storage services.

SkyFlok S3

Additionally, Chocolate Cloud is preparing to launch SkyFlok S3, an object storage service with a public S3 API which requires some privacy-sensitive processes to be hosted at the Edge or in the Cloud. Just like SkyFlok for Enterprise, the S3 interface is provided by a set of S3 Gateways. However, instead of the clients’ own infrastructure, these are deployed by CC to public cloud infrastructure. Currently CC is utilizing Fly.io to deploy S3 Gateways in different locations across Europe in an effort to reduce file access latency for a geographically varied user base.

3.3 System Architecture

An overview of the software components that make up the SkyFlok services can be seen on Figure 3. The most important dataflows and interfaces are also shown.

Figure 3: Overview of different all SkyFlok components, their interfaces and interactions.

Skyflok.com backend

The Skyflok.com backend is a set of microservices that manage all aspects related to file storage and sharing, user and team management and several connected aspects. All microservices have been written in Python and store entities in either a traditional relational database or in Google Datastore. It is a core component, shared by SkyFlok, SkyFlok for Enterprise and SkyFlok S3 services.

SkyFlok web application

The SkyFlok web application (Webapp) is a Javascript and VueJS application that is the sole interface used by SkyFlok users. It follows a thin client design approach, communicating with the backend through a REST API. To ensure scalability, it also performs encryption, erasure coding and manages transfers to and from the cloud storage locations.

On-premises Storage Gateway

The On-premises Storage Gateway component is an extension to the original SkyFlok deployment, developed as part of the SkyFlok for Enterprise solution. It is a self-hosted Python application that provides an industry-standard S3 interface for object storage. It is stateless, beyond a configurable file and metadata cache and performs all encryption, erasure coding and data transfer tasks typically performed by the user's browser. This component is not shown separately on Figure 3, but is very similar to the SkyFlok S3 Gateway in terms of its place in the system architecture. A key differentiator is its ability to also use SkyFlok edge devices as storage locations.

SkyFlok edge devices

To be able to offer a versatile edge storage solution for enterprises, CC has created a customized version of MinIO [13] that can be deployed by the customer onto existing infrastructure. This approach has been selected as it makes it possible to integrate a wide range of storage resources into SkyFlok for Enterprise.

SkyFlok S3 Gateway

The SkyFlok S3 Gateway is the equivalent of the On-premises Storage Gateway for the SkyFlok S3 service. It shares most of its features, but its implementation is significantly different as it has been designed to be deployed to a public cloud.

The following list contains an overview of the components that should be checked using static code analysis as well as the programming language in which they were written:

- SkyFlok backend microservices (Python),
- SkyFlok S3 Gateway (Python) and On-premises Storage Gateway (Python),
- SkyFlok.com webapp (Javascript, VueJS2),
- SkyFlok Object Storage Developer Portal (Typescript, VueJS 3),
- RLNC library used for erasure coding (C++).

3.4 Workflows

Here we present the high-level overview of SkyFlok's file upload and download workflows. These are provided as relevant examples, showcasing the interactions between many of the components of CC's supply chain. A more complete and detailed description of workflows will be provided later within the project to help establish the producer-consumer graph of components in the TBOM.

In SkyFlok, to achieve outstanding security and accessibility, files are encrypted and erasure-coded with added redundancy, and then the resulting fragments are distributed across multiple cloud storage providers and countries. SkyFlok runs these computations inside the client's browser without requiring the backend to carry out most security- and privacy-sensitive steps (e.g., encryption, Random Linear Network Coding). In SkyFlok for Enterprises and SkyFlok

S3, these steps are delegated to Gateways deployed either at the edge on the client’s private infrastructure or as a service running in a public cloud. In all three cases, the Skyflok.com backend as well as the storage locations exclusively interact with encrypted, erasure-coded data. The encryption keys are stored by the Skyflok.com backend.

Figure 4: Overview of SkyFlok file storage and retrieval.

Figure 4 shows a high-level view of how SkyFlok files are uploaded and retrieved. The erasure-coded fragments are distributed across the selected public cloud locations. The Skyflok.com backend coordinates the process, acting as a sort of conductor. File data is transferred directly between the browser and the cloud location. Retrieving files is quite similar and involves downloading enough erasure-coded fragments, then decoding and finally decrypting.

The whole process is coordinated with the use of a storage policy. A storage policy is like a recipe in the sense that it defines what encryption and erasure coding scheme is used (as well as the schemes’ parameters) and what chosen locations for the coded fragments are selected. Each SkyFlok customer has their own custom storage policy defined, based on their particular requirements as well as on their physical location.

To be able to connect a user directly with the fragments on the cloud and edge locations, pre-signed URLs are used. The links used to upload and download fragments are requested by the browser from the Skyflok.com backend. Because the links point to protected resources, they pose a security challenge. How can the browser be trusted with the credentials necessary to access these resources? The solution is to create a cryptographic signature and include it in the link. This creates a pre-signed URL which does not require additional credentials to access the protected resource. The URLs have a short lifespan and can generally only be used once. The signature is calculated using asymmetric-key cryptography and is guaranteed to be different every time. Figure 5 illustrates the steps taken when a file is downloaded using a pre-signed URL.

Figure 5: The steps required to download a file from SkyFlok using a pre-signed URL.

3.5 Infrastructure and Deployment

Infrastructure: One of the core challenges CC faces in attesting that its software is preserving the privacy and security of the data it stores for its customers comes from the lack of direct control over the infrastructure where the software is deployed to. As detailed in Section 3.3 and presented on Figure 3, the Skyflok.com backend is a set of microservices running on the Google Cloud Platform (GCP), using the Google App Engine environment. The On-premises Storage Gateway, as its name suggests, is deployed on a customer’s existing infrastructure and is monitored and managed by the customer, not CC. The SkyFlok S3 Gateway is currently deployed to Fly.io. Finally, SkyFlok users access the service using a web browser, a software component that is part of the chain, but also outside the supervision of CC.

Deployment mechanisms: Beyond the lack of control over the infrastructure, the deployment process itself can potentially be a security vulnerability. Fortunately, both GCP and fly.io have a strong security model that requires any changes to deployed services be made by developers in the possessions of a private key associated with the company. However, this still requires trust in the provider and makes a security audit more difficult as the infrastructure upon which CC’s services are running is not publicly documented.

3.6 Problem Statement

Fundamental problem: Privacy and security audits are crucial to gaining new customers and supporting new cloud storage providers in our ecosystem. Thus, automated and dynamic analysis mechanisms that can validate both CC’s own software and third-party software libraries and/or host systems are needed to scale the business. Furthermore, trusted third-party certifications for privacy and security can be eased and streamlined in the future, reducing operating costs. For example, one privacy certification may cost tens of thousands of Euros yearly aside from the internal costs of running the verification and certification process.

Static code security testing: One of the key building blocks to solving the problem lies in static code security analysis techniques. However, in order for them to work, they must be able to handle the complexities of the supply chain, the large number of dependencies and the varied hardware infrastructure. Through a comprehensive suite of traditional static code analysis testing, a list of alerts should be generated. The list should be complete, highlighting potential security vulnerabilities, while containing as few false positive alerts as possible. To make the solution holistic, all programming languages used by the pilot use case should be

supported.

Dynamic security testing: Many vulnerabilities are difficult to detect solely using static code analysis. Thus, a multi-pronged dynamic security testing approach must complement them. Special attention should be given to the infrastructure and deployment scenarios in which various different components operate, e.g. containerized microservices running on a public cloud or web applications running in a browser.

Continuous security assessment and assurance: The development of the pilot use case's components is ongoing. Manual security tests can easily miss important vulnerabilities due to the complexity of the task or simply human error. Thus, any type of security assessment must be carried out automatically, whenever any part of the supply chain changes. Given the complexity of the supply chain, it is difficult for the generated report to strike a balance between understandability and containing enough specific information that it becomes actionable (i.e., support developers in quickly fixing or mitigating security vulnerabilities). Finally, to increase confidence in the security level of the service, users could be presented with the outcomes of the assessment. However, for this to be effective, this report must be easy to read for non-technical users. More crucially, it must not leak any sensitive information.

3.7 Threat model

Chocolate Cloud has identified several potential security threats to its services.

Public interfaces: Attackers might try to compromise the security of SkyFlok's microservices through their public REST APIs in several possible ways. These potential vulnerabilities come mostly from undiscovered bugs in the software part of the supply chain from either consumed third-party libraries, their incorrect integration into the microservices or the microservice code itself. For example, an attacker might try to take advantage of these potential vulnerabilities to:

- access protected endpoints of the public API without valid user credentials,
- perform a privilege escalation attack,
- access internal (intra-service) endpoints that are not meant to be used by end-users,
- brute force or use a more sophisticated attack against two-factor authentication (2FA) and non-2FA user accounts,
- access the web-based administration and development tools used by Chocolate Cloud employees, e.g., phpMyAdmin and SkyFlok Admin web applications.

Infrastructure-specific threats: Some security issues stem from infrastructure-specific threats related to the hardware components of the supply chain. For instance, microservices deployed to public clouds may be collocated with other services that might try to steal private information through side channel attacks. Others may be related to software components. For example, an attacker might target the service deployment workflow itself. Thus, it would be beneficial if it was possible to verify that the deployed service instances are running the code CC intended to deploy (i.e. secure the container build and deployment process within Google Cloud and Fly.io).

Browser-based attacks: CC's product supply chain includes the users' browser. Similarly to infrastructure-related threats, CC has next-to-no control over this component. While it is possible to limit access to specific browsers and versions, this must be done with consideration to user experience. Such limitations are also easily circumvented and don't consider third-party browser plugins. A typical attack might try to compromise the browser-based credential storage of the Skyflok.com webapp and/or the S3 developer portal. This could be attempted using either cross-site scripting or from a different domain, running in the user's browser.

Known security vulnerabilities: Many of the aforementioned attacks involve an actor that utilizes a known security vulnerability (e.g.: incorrect use of cryptography) in either CC's codebase, in a software dependency, or in a hardware system in the supply chain. Thus, an automated solution that reliably and continuously detects such vulnerabilities is key to ensuring a swift fix.

3.8 Issues with Existing Approaches

Fundamental issue: There is a lack of automated and dynamic security auditing techniques for third-party software libraries and cloud software platforms/infrastructure. This creates massive challenges for security-driven and privacy-by-design solutions to have a complete overview of potential software- or hardware-related vulnerabilities in their supply chain. Specific components can be individually inspected, but this is costly and not always possible with third-party software libraries and rented shared deployment environments. Dynamic mechanisms that provide a holistic, automated, seamless validation and audit for security are currently not available.

Complexity: To provide a comprehensive security assessment solution that can manage the heterogeneity of the underlying hardware infrastructure and the software environment, multiple tools must be combined to assess the entire supply chain. While it is possible to build such a solution manually, even an expertly crafted one is likely to miss some of the underlying complexities. This is further exacerbated by the need to keep the solution up-to-date both with continuously updated software and hardware components and an evolving threat model.

Security expertise required: The security assessment reports generated by conventional static code analysis tools typically have a relatively high false positive alert rate. Thus, qualified personnel must evaluate the list of alerts, distinguish between actual issues and perceived issues. This requires special expertise, delays the process of addressing the identified vulnerabilities and may reduce the overall trust in the process for non-technical users.

Practical considerations: Small to medium companies may struggle to build a comprehensive solution due to costs. Beyond the initial investment, qualified personnel must be permanently assigned to oversee the security assessment process, limiting the time they can spend on other tasks. A non-automated process also has the possibility that it periodically overwhelms the available human resources. This leads to delays in addressing security issues, increasing the time a service is vulnerable.

3.9 Impact of RESCALE on the Pilot Use Case

As cybersecurity is becoming a critical business enabler and offering vulnerability-free solutions is a crucial factor for cloud storage, adding RESCALE's new supply chain security assessment features to CC's solutions will bring significant competitive advantages. In terms of evaluating the security of CC's product offering, two distinct areas emerge. Firstly, the relatively large code base with a complex list of dependencies will be checked using static code analysis tools. This is aimed at revealing known security vulnerabilities and bugs that may compromise security.

Secondly, the RESCALE Dynamic testing module will be employed to perform dynamic testing (e.g. penetration testing, runtime monitoring, etc.) of the Skyflok.com backend and gateways based on their OpenAPI descriptions. These run as microservices in a containerized, public cloud environment. Thus, a sandboxed environment will be constructed and components will be deployed to it and evaluated through mechanisms built in RESCALE. The potential threats that will be checked in the project have been described in Section 3.7.

Finally, the pilot use case will benefit from RESCALE's ability to automate security testing as an integrated part of the development pipeline. Conventional tests that validate software from a functional perspective can easily be integrated with existing CI/CD tools. A similar approach developed in RESCALE that continuously performs security assessments will ensure that an ever-developing product portfolio remains secure through a series of trusted updates. To achieve this, whenever an existing software component is updated or a new component is added, the TBOM must, similarly, be updated and maintained to reflect that particular component version so that the Trust Orchestrator Framework (TrustOR) can make decisions on the tests that must be performed. Any potential vulnerabilities that are identified can then swiftly be patched.

By focusing on the entire supply chain, RESCALE will create a holistic view that covers issues regardless of whether they come from the software or hardware side, from a consumed third-party library, a rented hosted hardware component or CC's own software.

3.10 Success criteria

The pilot use case's overarching goal is to convincingly show that through continuous security assessments performed using RESCALE-developed tools and services, Chocolate Cloud's products meet the high standards demanded by our customers. This involves using both static as well as dynamic code security testing. To maintain a high level of user trust, the testing should have a high coverage of component code and reports should contain a low number of false positive alarms. Furthermore, a wide range of attack scenarios should be considered, with special consideration to infrastructure-specific vulnerabilities and attack vectors. Given the highly distributed and constantly evolving nature of CC's code base and products, an automated approach is necessary.

4 Conclusions and Future Plans

This deliverable presented the specifications of RESCALE's two pilot use cases: *Auto-Placement Security Aware Augmented Data-Flow and Infrastructure* and *Privacy-by-Design Distributed Cloud and Edge Storage*. On the technical side, the architecture, data workflows and underlying infrastructure of both pilots were specified. This was followed by the problem definitions, any issues with existing approaches and finally how RESCALE will address the identified challenges.

While preparing this deliverable, the partners developing the two pilot use cases (PST and CC) consulted with the entire consortium and started preparing a list of functional and non-functional requirements. Thus, this deliverable, along with its final version (D2.2), will serve as input to Task 2.2 when capturing the project's requirements. The final version will also refine and expand the Use Cases specifications in M19 of the project, taking into consideration the outcomes of the project's first cycle.

References

- [1] Peer Stritzinger GmbH. Peer stritzinger gmbh public github, 2024. <https://github.com/stritzinger>, visited 2024-02-26.
- [2] Peer Stritzinger GmbH. Erlang opc-ua implementation, 2024. <https://github.com/stritzinger/opcua>, visited 2024-02-26.
- [3] Peer Stritzinger GmbH Luca Succi. Erlang ros2 implementation, dds, 2024. https://github.com/rosie-project/rosie_dds, visited 2024-02-26.
- [4] Peer Stritzinger GmbH. Grisp platform, 2024. <https://www.grisp.org>, visited 2024-02-26.
- [5] Chocolate Cloud ApS. Chocolate cloud website, 2024. <https://www.chocolate-cloud.cc>, visited 2024-01-10.
- [6] Konstantinos Kontodimas, Polyzois Soumplis, Aristotelis Kretsis, Panagiotis Kokkinos, Marcell Fehér, Daniel E. Lucani, and Emmanouel Varvarigos. Secure distributed storage orchestration on heterogeneous cloud-edge infrastructures. *IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing*, 11(4):3407–3425, 2023.
- [7] M. Sipos, J. Heide, D. Lucani, M. Pedersen, F. Fitzek, and H. Charaf. Adaptive Network Coded Clouds: High Speed Downloads and Cost-Effective Version Control. *IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing*, PP(99), 2015.
- [8] Florian Kelbert, Franz Gregor, Rafael Pires, Stefan Köpsell, Marcelo Pasin, Aurélien Havet, Valerio Schiavoni, Pascal Felber, Christof Fetzer, and Peter Pietzuch. Securecloud: Secure big data processing in untrusted clouds. In *Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE), 2017*, pages 282–285, 2017.
- [9] Marco Loaiza, Dimitris Chatzopoulos, Claudio Savaglio, Raffaele Gravina, and Spyros Lalis. Agents in the computing continuum: the mlsysops perspective. In *The 1st International Workshop on Machine Learning for Autonomic System Operation in the Device-Edge-Cloud Continuum (MLSysOps 2023), in conjunction with the International Conference on Embedded Wireless Systems and Networks (EWSN)*, Rende, Italy, 2023.
- [10] Aristotelis Kretsis, Panagiotis Kokkinos, Polyzois Soumplis, Juan Jose Vegas Olmos, Marcell Fehér, Márton Sipos, Daniel E. Lucani, Dmitry Khabi, Dimosthenis Masouros, Kostas Siozios, Paraskevas Bourgos, Sofia Tsekeridou, Ferad Zyulkyarov, Efstathios Karanastasis, Efthymios Chondrogiannis, Vassiliki Andronikou, Aitor Fernandez Gomez, Silviu Panica, Gabriel Iuhasz, Anastassios Nanos, Charalampos Chaliios, and Manos Varvarigos. Serrano: Transparent application deployment in a secure, accelerated and cognitive cloud continuum. In *2021 IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom)*, pages 55–60, 2021.
- [11] Szymonacedaski, Supratim Deb, Muriel Medard, and Ralf Koetter. How Good is Random Linear Coding Based Distributed Networked Storage? In *1st Workshop on Network Coding, Theory and Applications (NetCod)*, April 2005.
- [12] Chocolate Cloud ApS. Skyflok website, 2024. <https://www.skyflok.com>, visited 2024-01-10.

[13] MinIO Inc. Minio object storage for kubernetes, 2024.
<https://min.io/docs/minio/kubernetes/upstream/>, visited 2024-02-10.